

**ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN'S PARTICIPATION IN THE GLOBAL EUROBOND
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In this article in Uzbekistan there is capital the market situation In the economy of the republic held o the his to the economy effect, this of the system development hindrance doer arguments study, of the system negative consequences softening and capital the market new to stage take exit issue, fast measures to see light up given Thisin reforms in our country activity and the world of the community place light up given Our economy of subjects long term investments attraction to do andinternational capital to the market exit potential studied, analysis done. This the processdone increasing economy subjects in the activity face giving economic pointers was studied.

International capital to the market on the way out Uzbekistan authority by done being increased opportunities, theoretical and practical aids was analyzed. This is it of activity prospect for conclusion and Suggestions given Thisarticle three from the part consists of First in part of euro bonds appear be to be history, second and the third in parts of euro bonds release and of treatment to himself special features attention directed.

Euro bonds - this bond issued country or of countries from currency another in currency expressed debt securities. They are usually governments, international organizations or corporations by from international investors funds attraction to do issued for of Eurobonds some main Features:

- *Currency*: Eurobonds are usually different from the national currency of the issuer in currency is released. For example, Europe state USA dollar or Japanese in yenexpressed can issue bonds.

- *International market* : Eurobonds usually international capital in the markets will be issued, which will attract investment from the global financial markets to the issuers enable will give.

- *Diversification* : Eurobonds to issuers their own investor basediversification and wider funding beyond local investorsuse of resources opportunity will give.

- *Regulatory framework* : Regulation of countries issuing Eurobonds put requirements obeys. However, euro bonds according to sure the only one There is no regulatory framework and they have different legal and tax regimes can obey.

- *Income and risk* : of Eurobonds profitability different factors, including creditworthiness of the issuer, valid interest rates and the market on demand depends. High to the rating have organizations or strong credit have Eurobonds issued by countries with a lower credit rating or high level to risk have to those who than lower to income have will be

- *Maturity*: Eurobonds are short-term (for example, a few months) for various periods ranging from short to long-term (e.g. several decades).have to be possible

- *Trading* : Eurobonds are usually traded on the international secondary market, which where investors can buy and sell them ahead of time. This bonds most of the time big global in the stock exchanges to the list is taken or brokerdealers through off the stock market (OTC) for sale.

That's it to emphasize must eurobonds in euros issued bonds with mixed up do not send need Eurobonds of the issuer national from currency another each how in currency denomination can be done.

Euro bonds short term, medium and long term will be Shortterm up to 1 year, medium term 10 to 30 years and long term 40 up to in term is given. This bond type the first being in Italy issued and until now Europe in the states active moves. Such papers has the following characteristics:

- these are present doer valuable papers;
- one of time in itself one how many to markets placed;
- far away for a period of time is given
 - the rule as a 10-30 year (40 to the bottom);
- credit attraction done currency too issuer, too investor for foreign if;
- Eurobond dollar to the equivalent have;
- coupons according to percentages tax holding without remaining is paid;

The main purpose of the Eurobond issuer to issue this bond is to seek alternative financial resources. In addition to the euro bond issuer provides many conveniences. Save up to 20% on the cost of raising capital. The issuer of euro bonds to the capital market of several countries at the same time take out takes To the issuer less obligations is loading.

National banking international finance of institutions funds attraction reach

and of the economy leader networks modernization, priority and strategic investment projects financing according to the leader of the republic is a bank.

EUR debut issue of bonds by Uzmilliybank Citibank(USA), Natixis (France), SMBC Nikko (Japan) and Gazprombank (Russia) together with internationally recognized underwriting banks increased.

EUR The second impetus for the development of the bond market was the Vietnam War and from him come coming out from limitations come came out 1965 February in OY1 the president L. Johnson capital export optional restriction program announcement did (Voluntary Restraint Program). of the United States TMK subsidiary enterprises Europe in the markets funds to to the cloak encouraged. 1968 january in the month Johnson cabinet Joint From the states outside to investments to directly restrictionsput

That's it from the time starting from euro bonds of the market fast growth and necessary the period of emergence of infrastructure begins. American Morgan in 1968 Guaranty Bank created a clearinghouse for Euroclear bond trading, In 1970 his main competitor Cedel appeared it has been.

In 1969 euro bonds in the market the most big operators their own self- regulatory organization International Association of Bond Dealersthey made In the 90s she is International valuable papers market association (NAME) thatchanged.

In the 1970s capital for export of restrictions void to be done The euro has had no effect on the bond market, which is booming continued to develop. Another impetus for its development was in the early 80s global debt crisis it has been.

Euro bonds nomination done currency name with is called For example, Euroyen and Eurodollar bonds are denominated in Japanese yen and American, respectively in dollars is expressed. Euro bond when you say in the country legal payment means a bond issued in a currency different from the instrument.

It is euro currency in the market strictly profitable debt tool or valuable paper as works and 530 expires in a year. These bonds have low interest rates and zero forex risk have Thus, foreign to corporations to expand internationally in currency capital attraction to do enable will give. This in the term EUR the word bonds represent a foreign currency with a nominal value.

So he is also known as a foreign bond and derives its name from that currency. For example, in the USA Japanese in yen issued external bond European bond will be Euro bonds small capital to the market have attracts companies and is diverse to investors due to its small nominal value offers investment opportunities.

Although the term has the word "euro" in it, its to Europe or his currency never how connection no. SHE IS own name bonds nomination to be done from the euro currency takes for example eurodollars, euroyen, europound bonds, etc. Also he Capital letter "E" issued by the European Union and Eurozone countries started with difference from Eurobond does.

Raising money internationally through bond issuance and bank loans can be done. This is done in domestic and international markets. The difference is that money in international markets is usually different from the currency used by the borrower can come in currency. A characteristic feature of the international bond market is that bonds are always sold outside the borrower's country. There are three types of bonds, two of which are international bonds. Internal bond - this in the country resident by issued bond. A foreign bond is a bond issued by a foreign borrower in a specific country issued bond. Euro bonds one how many countries for sale and are writable bonds.

Issuer (has acquired the right to issue securities and paper money state, bank or office) for abroad in currency issued long term are securities. The credibility of the issuer is monitored by rating agencies goes Euro bonds 1 from 40 up to be ⁱ was for a period of time funds governments, international organizations, local issued by state authorities and large corporations. Issuer issued in foreign currency for (usually) international among foreign investors securities placed with the help of a syndicate of underwriters, they the rule for is treated as a security in the form of currency. "Euro" prefix that to be called to tradition respect as, because in Europe the first Euro is because bonds are issued and sold. Euro bonds basically in Europe is sold and will be placed. Euro bonds one type the dragon bonds (dragon bonds)- Asia (first in line Japan) in the market placed and Asia on the stock exchange usually in Singapore or in Hong Kong are placed Eurodollar bonds.

Foreign bonds - issued by the issuer in any foreign country issued in the currency of the country and placed in the currency of the country from the country underwriters of the syndicate help with placed. An example for: "Yankee" bonds - bonds in the Yankee USA (Yankee bonds); "Samurai" samurai bonds (Samurai bonds) "shibosai" shibosai bonds (Shibosai bonds), "daimyo" daimyo bonds (Damio bonds), today - In Japan shogun bonds; "Bulldog" in England bulldog bonds (Bulldog bonds); "Rembrandt" in Holland Rembrandt bonds (Rembrand bonds); "matador" Spanish matador bonds (Matador bonds); "kangaroo" in Australia kangaroo bonds (Kangaroo bonds) and others.

In short, the global euro bond market is an international financial operations fast developed is going This to standards answer giving personnel preparation now transfer need

has been from reforms the main ones is considered In the future euro bonds in the market of Uzbekistan participation expand international finance in the market capital resources share increase, of our personnel experiences to increase As a result right at the time and in space placed euro bonds efficiency to increase take will come. In economics economy of subjects wide in coverage euro bonds successful location capital of the resource big amount to accumulate and of course more directions in financing coverage provides. in our country investment attractiveness improves and our country international level high to the steps take emits

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